

The Unification of Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

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Abstract: This paper presents my quantum gravity theory, and only four-dimensional spacetime is sufficient to unify relativity and quantum mechanics. I briefly introduce the content firstly.

Measuring the surface pressure of an object to determine the mass of its mass center does not conform to the principles of modern science. I improve the connection of the values between measurement result and mass center based on the Biot-Savart Law, and re-calculate the gravitational constant G with the data from the original Cavendish Torsion scale experiment. Then I find the connection between G and vacuum permeability μ_0 , and the connection between mass and electric charge, and the connection between mass and magnetic flux.

Then I find that Michelson-Morley experiment proves the light bending effect in the moving reference frame is consistent with Lorentz transformation. Since mass is related to magnetic flux, special relativity can be explained by the bending effect of light wave. Based on Newton's theory of gravity, every object has attractive effect to the field in the space, so gravitational interaction is caused by the attraction from all the objects in universe. The attractive effect from target object is defined as the internal field, and the effect from all the other objects is defined as the external field. The coordinate systems of the two fields have the rotation relationship that is explained by Lorentz transformation, and then special relativity just describes the connection between internal wave and external wave, and Riemann curvature and wave function are equivalent to describe the gravitational interaction that is the coupling of the two waves as the generator or graviton. All the equations of special relativity can be derived in this way smoothly, and I also find there is the minimum and maximum bending effects in special relativity, and there is one vacuum and one vacuum light speed at each local scale.

Since special relativity describes the physical mechanism of gravitational interaction, I give the physical equation of metric tensor, and the general solution of field equation in general relativity. Then I prove the metric tensor is equivalent to wave function, and explain the physical significance of quantum probability, and Schrodinger equation is equivalent to field equation of general relativity. Also, I derive and clarify the uncertainty principle and quantum path integral are equivalent to space-time curvature of general relativity. Moreover, I give another equivalent equation form of Dirac equation to explain the spin quantum state intuitively. Hence quantum mechanics actually explains gravitational interaction in another mathematical form.

Finally, I derive to prove that electric field is caused by gravitational interaction, and electric field describes the quantum spin angular momentum, and spin quantum state corresponds to the generalized electric charge. Then I derive to give the gravitationization law of quantum to explain strong and weak interactions, and some physical effects, and give the quantization law of gravity in the form of complex matrix to unify the metric tensor and quantum mechanics in maths. In the end, spacetime is multi-scale, and force is caused by the interaction of all the matters in universe.

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1. The calculation and equation about gravitational constant G .	

1.1 Mass can not be directly measured:

Fig.01. the problem of measuring mass with a balance .

Refer to Fig.01 (left), when the object is static on a balance, the gravity and support force are balanced at mass center O by:

$$F_N = F_G = mg$$

Refer to Fig.01 (right), the pressure and support force are balanced at contact point A by:

$$F_p = -F_p \neq F_G$$

Although F_p is caused by F_G , they are not the same force rigorously because of different points of force application. Because all physical laws are equivalent in all inertial reference frames, the Biot-Savart Law can describe the connection between mass center O and contact point A :

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 qv \cdot \sin\theta}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{\mu_0 qv}{4\pi r^2} \quad (\theta = 90^\circ)$$

So:

$$\phi_m = B \cdot S = B \cdot 4\pi r^2 = \mu_0 \cdot qv$$

B connects to pressure p , and so magnetic flux ϕ_m connects to mass for the similar intrinsic property. The measurement result in Cavendish experiment is m_c , so the real mass:

$$m \propto m_c \cdot 4\pi r^2$$

1.2 The equation of mass:

In the original Cavendish torsion scale experiment (paper 'Experiments to determine the Density of the Earth' on <Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society> in 1798), the diameters of the big and small balls are per 30.48cm and 5.08cm by:

$$r_1 = 15.24 \times 10^{-2} m ; r_2 = 2.54 \times 10^{-2} m$$

G_c from Cavendish experiment:

$$G_c = \frac{k\theta r^2}{2m_{1c}m_{2c}L} = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ (N} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}^2)$$

Let $m_c \cdot 4\pi r^2$ instead of m_c :

$$\begin{aligned} G &= \frac{k\theta r^2}{(m_{1c} \cdot 4\pi r_1^2) \cdot (m_{2c} \cdot 4\pi r_2^2) \cdot 2L} = \left(\frac{k\theta r^2}{2m_{1c} \cdot m_{2c} \cdot L} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4\pi r_1^2 \cdot 4\pi r_2^2} \right) \\ &= (6.67 \times 10^{-11}) \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi(15.24 \times 10^{-2})^2 \cdot 4\pi(2.54 \times 10^{-2})^2} \\ &= 2.82 \times 10^{-8} \text{ (N} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}^2) \end{aligned}$$

According to Poisson equation: $\nabla^2\phi = 4\pi G \cdot \rho$, $4\pi G$ corresponds to electromagnetic relation. Then:

$$4\pi G = 3.54 \times 10^{-7} \text{ (N} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}^2)$$

The vacuum permeability:

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} = 12.56 \times 10^{-7} \text{ (Wb/(A} \cdot \text{m))}$$

Compare the values:

$$\frac{4\pi G}{\mu_0} = \frac{3.54 \times 10^{-7}}{12.56 \times 10^{-7}} \approx 0.28$$

The values of $4\pi G$ and μ_0 are within one order of magnitude, so they are considered as the same physical quantity. Result **0.28** proves that the accuracy of Cavendish torsion scale experiment is low several hundred years ago, that makes sense compared with the technology today. Then there are the equations:

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi G \tag{EQ01}$$

And so:

$$m = qv \tag{EQ02}$$

In the condition of EQ01 and EQ02, Newton’s gravitational law and electromagnetic law both work under the same mechanism. $\phi_m = \mu_0 \cdot qv = 4\pi Gm$ makes the connection between magnetic flux and mass. Electromagnetism describes the electromagnetic wave, so gravitation should be described in the form of wave as well. Hence let’s analyse relativity with the interaction of waves firstly, and then verify EQ01 and EQ02 with the theory finally.

2. Lorentz transformation describes the bending effect of wave.

2.1 Michelson-Morley experiment proves the bending of light:

Refer to Fig.02 below, it shows the path of light at Y -axis in Michelson-Morley experiment. The light path is bended in the reference frame under earth’s orbital speed v . Then, the speed of light to pass the distance L in earth’s frame is:

$$c_0 = \sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$$

In light wave’s own frame, the passing time:

Fig.02. Michelson-Morley experiment (Y-axis).

$$t = L/c$$

In earth's frame, the passing time:

$$t_0 = L/c_0 = L/\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$$

Then Lorentz factor:

$$\gamma = \frac{t_0}{t} = \frac{L/\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}{L/c} = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}$$

γ describes the bending effect of light wave in the frame with relative speed v .

2.2 Time dilation effect is caused by the bending of light:

Fig.03. light bending effect in space-time coordinate system.

Refer to Fig.03, \vec{L} describes the light wave in the space-time. The coordinate system (X, T)

$(\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0})$ rotates θ degree to become the system (X_0, T_0) ($\mathbf{v} > \mathbf{0}$). Obviously, the bending of light in a system is equivalent to the rotation of coordinate system in maths. Light wave passes the different coordinate distances in the two systems for both space and time. Suppose the light path is straight in the minimum time interval Δt , and the connection of two coordinate systems:

$$\gamma = \frac{dt_0}{dt}$$

Fig.04. Michelson-Morley experiment (X-axis).

Refer to Fig.04, the result of Michelson-Morley experiment is that there is no time difference for the returns of light waves at X-axis and Y-axis. Thus, light wave must have the same bending effect at X-axis . Hence Michelson-Morley experiment proves the bending effect of light wave occurs between two inertial reference frames with the relative speed v .

Since $dt_0 = \gamma \cdot dt > dt$, Lorentz transformation describes it takes longer time for light wave to pass the same distance in its original direction under the bending effect. The time is not more or less in any system, and Lorentz transformation is the connection of the two coordinate systems. Relativity and quantum mechanics both explain physical mechanism through the vector rotation, so it is reasonable that the two theories actually explain the same interaction.

3. The physical significance of the special relativity.

3.1 The equation of momentum connection:

Refer to Fig.05(left) below, all the objects with mass exert an attractive force on each other according to Newton’s gravitational law, so the space at local scale has the tendency to move in all the directions. For target object m , only two fields can describe the attractive effect: internal field and external field. Internal field describes the attractive effect from itself, and external field describes the combined effect from all the other objects in universe. In the minimum time interval Δt when a wave moves straightly, the two fields are described by internal wave \vec{ds} and

external wave \vec{ds}_0 .

Fig.05. the momentum connection .

Refer to Fig.05 (right), according to chapter 2, external wave is bending in the frame of m , so $\vec{ds}(\vec{BA})$ has the angle θ with $\vec{ds}_0(\vec{CB})$. And:

$$\vec{BA} \perp \vec{AC} ; |\vec{BA}| = ds = c \cdot dt ; |\vec{CB}| = ds_0 = c \cdot dt_0 = c \cdot \gamma \cdot dt$$

So:

$$|\vec{AC}|^2 = |\vec{CB}|^2 - |\vec{BA}|^2 = (c \cdot \gamma \cdot dt)^2 - (c \cdot dt)^2 = (\gamma^2 - 1)c^2 dt^2 = \gamma^2 v^2 dt^2$$

Divided by dt^2 at both sides:

$$(\gamma c)^2 - c^2 = (\gamma v)^2$$

Multiply m_0^2 at both sides:

$$(\gamma m_0 c)^2 - (m_0 c)^2 = (\gamma m_0 v)^2$$

Let $\gamma m_0 = m$:

$$(mc)^2 - (m_0 c)^2 = (mv)^2$$

Due to momentum relation:

$$p = mc , p_0 = m_0 c , p_s = mv$$

Finally:

$$p^2 - p_0^2 = p_s^2 \quad \dots\dots (EQ03)$$

dt_0 , m_0 , p_0 are for external wave, and dt , m , p are for internal wave, and p_s is the momentum of object m at local scale to describe the matter wave . Obviously, internal and external waves are like virtual particles, and matter wave is like real particle. Momentum p_s is the result of the interaction between internal and external waves.

EQ03 describes the momentum connection of waves in special relativity. For magnetic flux:

$$\phi_m = BS \cos \theta$$

Due to EQ03:

$$m_0 = \frac{m}{\gamma} = m \cdot \cos \theta$$

Hence $\phi_m = 4\pi Gm$ from chapter 1 is consistent with special relativity.

3.2 The mass-energy equation:

3.2.1 Energy equation of electromagnetic filed:

Fig.06. energy equation of electromagnetic field.

Refer to Fig.06, Henri Poincaré had below proof of energy in electromagnetism (Poincaré,H. (1905) The present and the future of Mathematical Physics. Science, 19 (485) ,1-15) :

The energy flux of electromagnetic field:

$$\vec{S} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \vec{E} \times \vec{B}$$

The momentum of electromagnetic field:

$$\vec{P}_{EM} = \frac{1}{c^2} \int \vec{S} dV$$

Then:

$$\|\vec{E}_{EM-Density}\| = \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_0} B^2 \right) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{E}{c} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}{\mu_0} E^2 = \epsilon_0 E^2$$

And:

$$\|\vec{P}_{EM-Density}\| = \frac{\|\vec{S}\|}{c^2} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\mu_0} EB = \frac{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}{\mu_0} E \left(\frac{E}{c} \right) = \frac{1}{c} \epsilon_0 E^2$$

Combine above two formulas:

$$\|\vec{P}_{EM-Density}\| = \frac{1}{c} \|\vec{E}_{EM-Density}\|$$

So:

$$\mathbf{p} = \frac{\mathbf{E}}{c}$$

3.2.2 The mass-energy equation based on the bending effect:

Due to EQ03:

$$(\mathbf{p})^2 - (\mathbf{p}_0)^2 = (\mathbf{p}_s)^2$$

Due to section 3.2.1, $\mathbf{p} = \frac{\mathbf{E}}{c}$, then:

$$\left(\frac{E}{c}\right)^2 - (m_0c)^2 = (mv)^2$$

And then:

$$\left(\frac{E}{c}\right)^2 = m_0^2c^2 + \gamma^2m_0^2v^2 = m_0^2(c^2 + \gamma^2 \cdot v^2) = m_0^2c^2\gamma^2 = m^2c^2$$

So:

$$E = mc^2$$

Therefore, special relativity and electromagnetsm are consistent to the bending effect of light wave, and have the same physical mechanism with the gravitational interaction.

3.3 The equation of energy connection:

Fig.07. the equation of energy connection.

Refer to Fig.07, $\|\vec{ds}_0\| = E_0$, $\|\vec{ds}\| = E$, Due to EQ03:
 $(mc)^2 - (m_0c)^2 = (mv)^2$

Multiply c^2 at both sides:

$$(mc^2)^2 - (m_0c^2)^2 = (mvc)^2$$

Due to section 3.2:

$$E = mc^2 , E_0 = m_0c^2$$

Let $\|\vec{ds}_s\| = E_s = mvc$, then:

$$E^2 - E_0^2 = E_s^2 \quad \text{..... (EQ04)}$$

EQ04 describes the energy connection in special relativity. $E_s = p_s c = mvc$ describes the virtual energy of internal wave in the external field.

3.4 The equation of holonomic energy:

Due to EQ04 :

$$(mc^2)^2 - (m_0c^2)^2 = (mvc)^2$$

Devided by mc^2 at both sides:

$$mc^2 - \frac{1}{\gamma} m_0c^2 = mv^2$$

So:

$$E - \frac{1}{\gamma} E_0 = mv^2$$

Let:

$$E_i = mv^2 = mc_i^2 \quad \dots\dots (EQ05)$$

The Lagrangian in special relativity:

$$\mathcal{L} = -m_0c^2 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = -E_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = -\frac{1}{\gamma} E_0$$

Due to EQ05:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{\gamma} E_0 = mv^2 - mc^2 = E_i - E$$

Thus, $E_i = mv^2$ describes the holonomic energy of the matter wave at local scale. Since E_i is caused by the interaction of any two waves, $E_i = mc_i^2$ describes light speed is variable at the different scales, and vaccum is actually the minimum energy condition at each local scale.

3.5 The minimum bending effect:

Fig.08. The minimum bending effect .

Refer to Fig.08 (left), the sub-space at local scale is generated by two virtual waves \vec{ds}_1 and \vec{ds}_2 . If $E_1 \neq E_2$, they have the angle θ under the bending effect. Lorentz transformation is to consider one wave in the coordinate system of the other one, but in the bottom space at the larger scale, two waves are both bending because of the interaction, and the wave with lower energy has the larger rotation angle. Thus, the bending effect is higher when $v > 0$.

Refer to Fig.08 (right), if $E_1 = E_2$, $v = 0$, two waves are still parallel after the bending, and the bending effects of them are equal in the larger coordinate system. So the rotation angle:

$$\alpha = 45^\circ \quad (\theta = 0^\circ)$$

Before bending:

$$ds_1 = ds_2 = ds = c \cdot dt$$

After bending:

$$ds' = ds / \cos \alpha = \sqrt{2} c \cdot dt$$

Due to EQ04:

$$\frac{E'}{E} = \frac{\|ds\|}{\|ds'\|} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

So:

$$E'^2 = \frac{1}{2} E^2 \quad \dots\dots (EQ06)$$

EQ06 describes the minimum bending effect of wave in the bottom space. In this condition, internal and external waves do not bend relatively to each other, but each wave bends relatively to its original direction. Hence EQ06 is the necessary supplement to special relativity.

3.6 Special relativity describes the physical effect of Riemannian curvature:

3.6.1 The physical significance of metric tensor in special relativity:

Fig.09. the physical effect of Riemannian curvature .

Refer to Fig.09 (left), after \vec{Z} translates along the parallelogram formed by \vec{X} and \vec{Y} for a lap, if \vec{Z}' has the angle θ with \vec{Z} , the space is curved. This is the definition of Riemannian curvature, and it is described by:

$$R(\vec{X}, \vec{Y})\vec{Z} = \nabla_{\vec{X}}\nabla_{\vec{Y}}\vec{Z} - \nabla_{\vec{Y}}\nabla_{\vec{X}}\vec{Z} - \nabla_{[\vec{X}, \vec{Y}]}\vec{Z}$$

Let $\vec{X} = \overrightarrow{ds}$, $\vec{Y} = \overrightarrow{ds_0}$ based on the bending effect, and \overrightarrow{ds} and $\overrightarrow{ds_0}$ are the basis vectors of the coordinate systems of internal field and external field. Refer to Fig.09 (right), the rotation of \vec{Z} is equivalent to the rotation of coordinate system in the space. In special relativity, \vec{X} and \vec{Y} are equal as the constant \vec{c} in the inertial reference frames with the different basis

vectors. When \vec{X} and \vec{Y} are basis vectors of the subspace:

$$\nabla_{[\vec{X}, \vec{Y}]} = \mathbf{0}$$

Then:

$$R(\vec{X}, \vec{Y})\vec{Z} = [\nabla_{\vec{X}}, \nabla_{\vec{Y}}]\vec{Z}$$

Due to EQ03:

$$Y^j = \gamma \cdot X^i, \quad \partial_i = \gamma \cdot \partial_j, \quad Y^i = X^j / \gamma, \quad \partial_j = \partial_i / \gamma$$

So:

$$[\nabla_{\vec{X}}, \nabla_{\vec{Y}}] = X^i \partial_i (Y^j \partial_j) - Y^i \partial_i (X^j \partial_j) = X^i \partial_i (\gamma \cdot X^j \partial_j) - X^j \partial_i / \gamma (X^i \cdot \partial_j)$$

Then:

$$[\nabla_{\vec{X}}, \nabla_{\vec{Y}}] = X^i \partial_i (X^i \partial_i) - X^j \partial_j (X^j \partial_j) = X^i \partial_i (X^i \partial_i) - Y^j \partial_j (Y^j \partial_j) = \|\vec{ds}\|^2 - \|\vec{ds}_0\|^2$$

Due to EQ04:

$$[\nabla_{\vec{X}}, \nabla_{\vec{Y}}] = E^2 - E_0^2 = E_s^2$$

Thereby, the energy connection or momentum connection in special relativity describes the curved space (curved scale) actually, and Riemannian curvature is the mathematical form to describe the special relativity in the flat external field (flat scale). More over, Lie bracket also describes the connection of two vectors to generate the subspace. Due to below calculation:

$$[\nabla_i, \nabla_j] = ds_0^2 - ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 (\gamma^2 - 1) = c^2 dt^2 \cdot \gamma^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2} = v^2 \cdot dt_0^2 = ds_s^2$$

$ds_s^2 = (v dt_0)^2$ or $E_s^2 = (m v c)^2$ describes the relative motion of the target object in the flat space (scale), so relative speed v or momentum $p_i = m v$ or the holonomic energy $m v^2 = m c_i^2$ describes the matter wave of the object in the generative subspace. Hence metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ in Riemannian curvature describes the interaction of internal and external waves.

3.6.2 Minkowski metric tensor describes the bending effect at local flat scale:

Based on section 3.6.1:

$$ds_0^2 - ds^2 = ds_s^2$$

Since \vec{ds} and \vec{ds}_0 are opposite:

$$ds^2 = - ds_0^2 + v^2 \cdot dt_0^2$$

Then:

$$(c \cdot dt)^2 = - (c \cdot dt_0)^2 + (v \cdot dt_0)^2$$

Let $c = 1$:

$$dt^2 = - dt_0^2 + v^2 \cdot dt_0^2$$

Just considering the scalar in maths, and for \vec{ds}_s in the orthogonal sub-space:

$$dt^2 = ds^2, \quad ds_s^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2$$

Let $dt_0^2 = dt^2$ for simplified form:

$$ds^2 = - dt^2 + dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2$$

It is the Minkowski metric tensor for the line element ds that describes the straight light

wave in the minimum time interval ds . Another form with matrix is:

$$ds^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} \cdot dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

The Minkowski metric:

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = \mathbf{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1) = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The external field does not change in the inertial reference frame, so $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ describes the interaction of waves at local flat scale. Riemannian curvature describes the curved space through the mathematical form of coordinate system's rotation, and the bending effect of the wave is the actual physical mechanism explained by special relativity.

3.7 The physical significance of the constant light speed:

Fig.10. the constant light speed at local scale .

Refer to Fig.10, when a wave moves in the space, light speed c_i is its linear speed in the time interval Δt_i . For example, at the smaller scale of Δt_1 , light speed is c_1 in the direction of the motion trajectory. At the larger scale of Δt_2 , light wave is always bending to change the directions at each smaller scale under the variable external field. In the linear direction of the wave in Δt_2 , light speed satisfies below condition:

$$g^{-1}c_2 g = c_2$$

g is the matrix for the interaction to change light speed in the original direction, and g^{-1} is the inverse transformation, so light speed c_2 is constant at the local scale of Δt_2 . Thus, there is one light speed c_i at each flat local scale. When $\theta = 90^\circ$, $\vec{ds} \perp \vec{ds}_0$, $v = c$, so:

$$E_0 = E \cdot \cos \theta = E \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} = E \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = 0$$

In this condition, internal wave and external wave do not interact with each other. This is the maximum bending effect, and \vec{ds}_0 is in the null space of \vec{ds} . There is no resistance for internal

wave, so that c_i is the vacuum light speed at each local scale.

In all, special relativity describes the physical mechanism of interaction. Due to EQ03, EQ04:

$$\gamma = \frac{dt_0}{dt} = \frac{ds_0}{ds} = \frac{m}{m_0} = \frac{p}{p_0} = \frac{E}{E_0}$$

Hence all the physical quantities are decided by time interval Δt only, and there is only one variable of time in physics.

4. The physical mechanism of gravitation in general relativity.

4.1 Proper time is the condition of non-inertial reference frame:

The geodesic equation:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\lambda}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma^{\lambda}_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau} = 0$$

Fig.11. proper time is the condition of non-inertial reference frame .

Refer to Fig.11 (left), the interaction described by special relativity is based on the constant external field at local scale. The geodesic equation is based on the scale of proper time $d\tau$, so ds_0 of external wave in $d\tau = dt$ is smaller than in dt_0 in the inertial reference frame.

Refer to below Fig.11 (right), it is equal to that there is another object in external field with momentum $p_s = mv$, and $\overrightarrow{ds_0}$ is bending under the interaction with p_s . $ds_0(d\tau)$ is the projection of the bended $ds_0(dt_0)$ in the original direction. The interaction with p_s is actually the external force on the original system, and it causes the rotation of coordinate system of $\overrightarrow{ds_0}$, so that the target obejct who causes \overrightarrow{ds} is in non-inertial reference frame at the scale of $d\tau$. And the relation $\overrightarrow{ds} \perp \overrightarrow{ds_s}$ does not hold in this condition.

4.2 The physical equation of metric tensor in general relativity:

Fig.12. physical equation of metric tensor in general relativity.

Refer to Fig.12 (left), \vec{ds} , \vec{ds}_0 , \vec{ds}_s have the relation of a general triangle at the scale of $d\tau$ in the non-inertial reference frame. Let \vec{ds}_0 and \vec{ds}_s are basis vectors of the coordinate system in the sub-space, and then:

$$ds_0 = \vec{e}_\mu \cdot dx^\mu, \quad ds_s = \vec{e}_\nu \cdot dx^\nu$$

Like Minkowski metric:

$$ds^2 = (\vec{e}_\mu \cdot dx^\mu) \cdot (\vec{e}_\nu \cdot dx^\nu) = g_{\mu\nu} \cdot dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

And metric tensor:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = g(\vec{e}_\mu, \vec{e}_\nu) = \vec{e}_\mu \cdot \vec{e}_\nu \quad (\mu, \nu = 0, 1, 2, 3)$$

Refer to Fig.12 (right), make a circle with radius ds_s , and make the tangent of the circle to satisfy:

$$\vec{ds}_0' \perp \vec{ds}_s'$$

Let $\|\vec{ds}_0'\| = E_0' = q \cdot E_0$ ($q > 0$):

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = q^2 E_0^2 \quad \dots\dots (EQ07)$$

EQ07 is the physical equation of metric tensor in general relativity. E , E_0 , E_s are all the real energies of the waves. The operation of $q \cdot E_0$ transform the non-flat scale to the flat scale in $d\tau$, in order to simplify the complex mathematical form of Riemannian curvature to the simple physical equation.

Let $ds = a$, $ds_0 = b$, $ds_s = c$. There is the form of $g_{\mu\nu}$:

$$a^2 = g_{00}b^2 + g_{01}bc + g_{10}cb + g_{11}c^2$$

Plus $(-b^2)$ at both sides:

$$a^2 - b^2 = g_{00}b^2 + g_{01}bc + g_{10}cb + g_{11}c^2 - b^2$$

Let $g_{00}b^2 + g_{01}bc + g_{10}cb + g_{11}c^2 - b^2 = q^2 \cdot c^2$:

$$a^2 - b^2 = q^2 c^2$$

So EQ07 satisfies $g_{\mu\nu}$ in maths, and $g_{\mu\nu}$ describes the connection of two coordinate systems in general relativity as well.

4.3 The time metric equation in general relativity:

Due to EQ07:

$$(mc^2)^2 - (mvc)^2 = q^2(m_0c^2)^2$$

Divided by m^2c^4 at both sides:

$$1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} = q^2 \cdot \frac{m_0^2}{m^2}$$

Let $\gamma_g = \frac{m}{m_0} = \frac{dt_0}{dt}$:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma_g^2} = \frac{1}{q^2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = \frac{1}{q^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma^2}$$

Since $q > 0$:

$$\gamma_g = q\gamma$$

Time dilation effect in general relativity:

$$\gamma_g^2 = q^2\gamma^2 = \frac{dt_0^2}{dt^2} = \frac{ds_0^2}{ds^2} = \frac{m^2}{m_0^2} = \frac{p^2}{p_0^2} = \frac{E^2}{E_0^2} \dots\dots (EQ08)$$

Due to EQ08:

$$dt^2 = \frac{1}{\gamma_g^2} \cdot dt_0^2$$

Considering the opposite directions:

$$g_{00} = -\frac{1}{\gamma_g^2} = -\frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \dots\dots (EQ09)$$

EQ09 is the time metric in general relativity to describe the connection of two coordinate systems through the connection of the time intervals.

4.4 The physical significance of kinetic energy:

Refer to Fig.13 (left) below, there are many objects at the same scale in universe, so the matter wave of target object must interact with the external matter wave in the larger scale. Let E_{se} ($e = \text{external}$) be the energy of external matter wave at the scale of $d\tau$ in the radial direction. When E_{se} is constant, $E_s = E_{se}$ is the condition of the flat local scale.

Refer to Fig.13 (right) below, the matter wave of target object has the minimum bending effect at the flat larger scale. Due to EQ06:

$$E_s'^2 = \frac{1}{2} E_s^2 = \frac{1}{2} m^2 v^2 c^2 = \left(\frac{1}{2} m v^2\right) (m c^2) = E_k \cdot E$$

Based on section 3.6.1, $[\nabla_{\bar{x}}, \nabla_{\bar{y}}] = \mathbf{E}_s^2$ describes the interaction of internal and external waves, and $\frac{1}{2}[\nabla_{\bar{x}}, \nabla_{\bar{y}}]$ describes the antisymmetry of covariant derivatives, so $\mathbf{E}_k \cdot \mathbf{E}$ describes the scaling of internal wave \vec{ds} , and \mathbf{E}_k is the scaling factor.

Fig.13. the physical significance of kinetic energy .

Thus, $\mathbf{E}_k = \frac{1}{2}m\mathbf{v}^2$ describes the energy of matter wave in the radial direction at the flat local scale. The external field on the earth is very stable, so \mathbf{E}_k is the kenetic energy in classical mechanics. Hence Newtonian limit is not the condition of low-speed and weak-field, and it is for the flat local scale actually. Since gravitational potential φ is in the radial direction:

$$|\mathbf{E}_p| = E_k$$

Then:

$$m \cdot \varphi = \frac{1}{2}m\mathbf{v}^2$$

So:

$$\mathbf{v}^2 = 2\varphi$$

Therefore, kinetic energy is the energy of matter wave in the radial direction at the flat local scale, and \mathbf{E}_k corresponds to \mathbf{E}_p in the gravitational field.

4.5 The physical significance of field equation in general relativity:

The following field equation in general relativity consists of the geometrical part on the left and physical part on the right:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$$

It can be explained and solved with the previous corresponding physical equations.

4.5.1 The physical mechanism of relativistic gravitation:

Fig.14. physical mechanism of relativistic gravitation .

Refer to Fig.14 (up), in the flat space-time, external wave \vec{ds}_0 is constant in the vacuum based on section 3.7. In Poisson’s equation:

$$\nabla^2 \varphi = 4\pi G \rho$$

Suppose g_1 is the acceleration caused by internal field, and g_2 is caused by external field. They are opposite in the flat space-time, so:

$$g = g_1 - g_2$$

Since:

$$g = \nabla \varphi = \frac{GM}{r^2}$$

So:

$$\frac{\nabla F_G}{m} = \nabla g = \nabla^2 \varphi$$

And $g_2 = \text{constant}$:

$$\nabla g = \nabla(g_1 - g_2) = \nabla g_1 = \nabla^2 \varphi = 4\pi G \rho$$

Thereby, ρ describes the variation of gravitational field with the position. Based on section 4.4, E_k corresponds to E_p at flat local scale, and E_s^2 and E_k have a linear relationship, so E^2 and E_k have a linear relationship due to EQ07. Due to EQ08, E^2 and ds^2 have the inverse proportion, so that gravitational field described by g has the inverse proportion with r^2 , that is already described by Newton’s law.

Refer to Fig.14 (down), in the curved space-time, \vec{ds} of target object M is bending under the interaction with \vec{ds}_0 and they are not in the radial direction as in the flat space-time. \vec{ds}_s actually describes gravitaitonal field in the radial direction under the interaction between internal and external waves. Thus, in general reativity, the time dilation effect must be considered.

4.5.2 The general solution of field equation:

Newton's law in Carton theory is:

$$R_{00} = \nabla^2 \varphi$$

$R_{\mu\nu}$ describes $[\vec{\nabla}_{\vec{X}}, \vec{\nabla}_{\vec{Y}}]$ in Riemannian curvature tensor $R(\vec{X}, \vec{Y})\vec{Z}$ at flat local scale, so internal field is considered as the gravitational field in the radial direction in Carton theory. Due to the second Bianchi identity:

$$\nabla_{\lambda} R^{\mu}{}_{\sigma\mu\nu} + \nabla_{\mu} R^{\mu}{}_{\sigma\nu\lambda} + \nabla_{\nu} R^{\mu}{}_{\sigma\lambda\mu} = 0$$

And to satisfy energy conservation:

$$\nabla^{\mu} T_{\mu\nu} = \nabla^{\mu} G_{\mu\nu} = 0$$

Then there is the field equation:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

Bianchi identity eliminates the divergence of curvature, so that field equation describes the flat local scale, and make gravitational field correspond to $\overrightarrow{ds_s}$ at the larger scale described by $G_{\mu\nu}$. The gravitational field in the radial direction and the bending internal field have connection of time dilation effect in $G_{\mu\nu}$. Multiply $g^{\mu\nu}$ at both sides of field equation:

$$g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}$$

Then:

$$R - \frac{1}{2} R \delta_{\mu}^{\mu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T$$

Since $\delta_{\mu}^{\mu} = 4$ in four-dimensional space-time:

$$R = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T$$

It describes the curvature and energy-momentum are equivalent for the holonomy system. When there are no other objects with p_s at the scale, it is the condition of vacuum for:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (\mu \neq 0 \ \& \ \nu \neq 0)$$

Since $T_{00} = -T$ for $\eta_{\mu\nu}$:

$$-\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{00} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot \rho c^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot \frac{\nabla^2 \varphi}{4\pi G} \cdot c^2 = \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla^2 (2\varphi)$$

And:

$$R = 2R_{00} = 2 \cdot \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla^2 \varphi = \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla^2 (2\varphi)$$

Newtonian limit is actually the normal condition of vacuum in relativity, so $R \neq 0$ inside the system, so the field equation holds internally. Due to EQ09, since $q = 1$ in the vacuum:

$$g_{00} = -\frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) = -\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right)$$

Since $[\nabla_{\bar{x}}, \nabla_{\bar{y}}]$ describes $G_{\mu\nu}$, for the holonomic curvature:

$$G_{00} = \nabla^2 g_{00} = -\nabla^2 \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla^2(v^2)$$

Since:

$$G_{00} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{00} = \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla^2(2\varphi)$$

So:

$$v^2 = 2\varphi = \frac{2GM}{r}$$

$v^2 = 2\varphi$ corresponds to the gravitational field without the bending effect of the waves. Considering the time dilation effect, the time metric in the vacuum is:

$$g_{00} = -\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)$$

It corresponds to the Schwarzschild metric in the vacuum correctly:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2(\sin\theta)^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Schwarzschild metric describes the gravitational field in the radial direction is weaker than in Newton's law because of the bending effect, so:

$$\varphi_{real} < \frac{GM}{r}$$

Due to EQ09 in the non-vacuum:

$$g_{00} = -\frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = -\frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)$$

Then the general metrics:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (q^2) \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2(\sin\theta)^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

And:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1/q^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \dots\dots (EQ10)$$

EQ10 is the general solution of field equation in general relativity in non-inertial reference

frame. The diagonal matrix $g_{\mu\nu}$ improved based on $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ transforms the connection at non-flat scale to the connection at the larger flat local scale including the other objects p_s . It is similar with unitary transformation in quantum mechanics, that will be involved in chapter 6.

4.6 The explanation of the orbit equation:

Due to Schwarzschild metric and geodesic equation, the planetary orbit equation:

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{u}}{d\phi^2} + \left(\mathbf{u} - \frac{3GM}{c^2} \mathbf{u}^2 \right) = \frac{GM}{h^2}$$

In maths, $G = 1$, $m = 1$, $c = 1$ to simplify calculation, so:

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{r} = \frac{GM}{r} = \varphi$$

$\left(-\frac{3GM}{c^2} \mathbf{u}^2 \right)$ is just the additional term compared with Newton's law. The orbit equation describes the connection between φ and angular momentum. According to section 4.5:

$$\varphi_{real} = \mathbf{u} - \frac{3GM}{c^2} \mathbf{u}^2 = \mathbf{u} \left(1 - \frac{3GM}{c^2} \mathbf{u} \right) = \frac{GM}{r} \left(1 - \frac{3GM}{rc^2} \right) < \frac{GM}{r}$$

So:

$$F_G < \frac{GMm}{r^2}$$

The orbit equation actually proves that the real gravitation F_G is smaller than the force in Newton's law. Thus, the work done by gravitation is smaller than in Newton's law, and so it takes more time for the real gravitational field to make the planet return to the state with the original momentum. That is the real reason of planetary precession.

About light bending effect, the equation is:

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{u}}{d\phi^2} + \left(\mathbf{u} - \frac{3GM}{c^2} \mathbf{u}^2 \right) = \mathbf{0}$$

There is no angular momentum of object in the equation, so light wave has no momentum p_s at the local scale, that is consistent to the physical mechanism in special relativity. Hence it is the wrong explanation that the static mass of the photon is zero. Mass is the intrinsic property of any matter, and it can not change until the internal structure is broken.

Moreover, φ_{real} describes the gravitational field in the vacuum already, and it does not matter with the speed v of the other object in the field. In fact, the planets with any speed v will weaken one's gravitational field according to the interaction described by relativity.

4.7 The Lagrangian and Hamiltonian in general relativity:

Due to EQ07:

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = q^2 \cdot E_0^2$$

Then:

$$m^2 c^4 - m^2 v^2 c^2 = q^2 m_0^2 c^4$$

Divided by mc^2 at both sides:

$$mc^2 - mv^2 = q^2 \frac{m_0}{m} m_0 c^2 = q^2 \frac{1}{\gamma_g} m_0 c^2$$

Due to EQ08, $\gamma_g = q\gamma$:

$$mc^2 - \frac{q}{\gamma} m_0 c^2 = mv^2$$

Since:

$$mv^2 = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} mv^2 \right) = 2T = (T + V) + (T - V) = \mathcal{H} + \mathcal{L}$$

So:

$$\mathcal{L} = T - V = -\frac{q}{\gamma} m_0 c^2 \quad \text{..... (EQ11)}$$

$$\mathcal{H} = T + V = mc^2 \quad \text{..... (EQ12)}$$

EQ11 describes the Lagrangian, and EQ12 describes the Hamiltonian in general relativity. The equations are related to E_k , so \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{H} are for the holonomic system at flat local scale. According to general relativity, the two special energies and potential energies V are clear to understand. \mathcal{H} describes the inherent energy for target object, and \mathcal{L} describes the energy of external field for the environment. V describes the energy of the field out of the local scale.

In all, gravitational field is caused by the interaction of internal and external waves in proper time $d\tau$, and Riemannian curvature is consistent to gravitational interaction. Additionally, the physical equations of $g_{\mu\nu}$ and $R_{\mu\nu}$ can simplify the mathematical calculation and understand the physical mechanism effectively.

5. General relativity is equivalent to quantum mechanics.

5.1 The physical significance of reduced Planck constant \hbar :

Due to EQ08:

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = \frac{dt_0}{dt} = \gamma_g$$

So:

$$E \cdot dt = E_0 \cdot dt_0 = \text{constant}$$

Then for any wave:

$$E_i \cdot \Delta t_i = \hbar \quad \text{..... (EQ13)}$$

\hbar is the reduced Planck constant to describe the angular momentum of any wave in the corresponding time interval Δt_i . Let $h = 2\pi\hbar$, $T_i = 2\pi\Delta t_i$ for periodic waves, due to EQ13:

$$E_i = \frac{\hbar}{\Delta t_i} = \frac{2\pi \cdot \hbar}{2\pi \cdot \Delta t_i} = \frac{h}{T_i} = h\nu_i$$

ν_i is the frequency, and $E_i = h\nu_i$ describes the energy of a wave. Let $E_i = \mathbf{p}_i \cdot \mathbf{c}$,
 $d\mathbf{s}_i = \mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{c} \cdot \Delta t_i$:

$$\hbar = \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{c} \cdot \Delta t_i = \mathbf{p}_i \mathbf{x}_i$$

\mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{p}_i of a wave are important physical quantities in quantum mechanics, and they can be explained by general relativity very well. Based on above derivation, \hbar is not the minimum piece of energy, and actually all the waves have the same \hbar .

5.2 The physical significance of De Broglie wave:

Due to EQ04, the energy of matter wave:

$$E_s = m\mathbf{v}\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{p}\mathbf{c}$$

Due to EQ13:

$$E_s = h\nu$$

Since $\mathbf{c} = \lambda\mathbf{f} = \lambda\nu$:

$$\lambda = \frac{\mathbf{c}}{\nu} = \frac{E_s/\mathbf{p}}{\nu} = \frac{h \cdot \nu}{\mathbf{p} \cdot \nu} = \frac{h}{\mathbf{p}}$$

Thus, De Broglie wave equation is also consistent to the relativity. Matter wave is caused by the gravitational interaction, so the physical mechanism of quantum mechanics should be same with gravitation.

5.3 Wave function is equivalent to the metric tensor:

5.3.1 $f(x) = e^{ikx}$ at flat local scale corresponds to Minkowski metric:

Fig.15. the form of complex number for energy connection in special relativity.

Due to section 5.2, the wave number:

$$k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi}{h/p} = \frac{p}{h/2\pi} = \frac{p}{\hbar}$$

Due to EQ13:

$$kx = \frac{p}{\hbar} \cdot c \cdot \Delta t = \frac{pc \cdot \Delta t}{E \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{E_s}{E}$$

Based on Euler equation:

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta$$

Refer to Fig.15, Let $\theta = kx$:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\|\overrightarrow{ds_s}\|}{\|\overrightarrow{ds}\|} = \frac{E_s}{E}, \quad \sin \theta = \frac{\|\overrightarrow{ds_0}\|}{\|\overrightarrow{ds}\|} = \frac{E_0}{E}$$

Thus, $\cos \theta = kx$ is for the projection of internal wave on real number axis, and $\sin \theta$ is for the projection of internal wave on imaginary axis. So the real number describes matter wave, and the imaginary number describes external wave. Then $f(x) = e^{ikx}$ describes the connection:

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = E_0^2$$

It is EQ04 in special relativity. Hence $f(x) = e^{ikx}$ corresponds to Minkowski metric in the form of complex number when e^{ikx} describes the matter wave at flat local scale. In the complex plane, real number axis is perpendicular to imaginary number axis, that is consistent to $\overrightarrow{ds_s} \perp \overrightarrow{ds_0}$ in special relativity. The time item dt^2 describes external wave in Minkowski metric, so imaginary number describes the time in wave function.

5.3.2 $\psi(x, t) = e^{i(kx - \omega t)}$ corresponds to metric tensor at non-flat local scale:

Fig.16. the form of complex number for energy connection in general relativity.

Due to EQ13, the angular frequency:

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi}{E_i} = 2\pi\nu_i = 2\pi \frac{E_i}{h} = \frac{E_i}{\hbar}$$

Then:

$$\omega t = \frac{E_i \cdot \Delta t}{\hbar} = \frac{E_i \cdot \Delta t}{E \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{E_i}{E}$$

Refer to Fig.16, let $kx = \alpha$, $\omega t = \beta$, then:

$$\theta = \alpha - \beta = kx - \omega t$$

Thus, rotate \vec{ds} by β degree to have the wave function in non-inertial reference frame:

$$\psi(x, t) = f(x)g(t) = e^{i\alpha}e^{-i\beta} = e^{ikx}e^{-i\omega t} = e^{i(kx-\omega t)}$$

Let $E_s = E_s(\theta)$, based on 5.3.1:

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = E^2 - E_s(\theta)^2 = E_0^2$$

Let $E_s = E_s(\alpha)$, then:

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = E^2 - E_s(\alpha)^2 = (qE_0)^2$$

This is EQ07 to describe metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ in general relativity. Thus, $\psi(x, t)$ describes the rotation of vector or the rotation of coordinate system at non-flat local scale. $-\omega t$ describes the variation of external field along the time t . e^{ikx} describes the wave direction at the larger flat scale, and $i(kx - \omega t) = i\theta$ describes the phase position of the wave, and $-\omega t$ describes the phase rotation of the wave. Hence wave function is the equivalent mathematical form of metric tensor in general relativity to describe the gravitational interaction.

5.3.3 The physical significance of probability amplitude:

Fig.17. the physical significance of probability amplitude .

Refer to Fig.17, each wave is continuously bending in the sub-spaces because of the variable external field, and it is in the linear direction in the holonomic space. ϕ_i is the eigenstate of the wave in each sub-space by:

$$\phi_i = e^{i(kx-\omega_i t)}$$

Take the derivative to t :

$$\phi_i' = -i\omega_i \cdot e^{i(kx-\omega_i t)}$$

Let $c_i = ik_i$:

$$\phi_i' = c_i \phi_i$$

Then the Born's rule:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_i c_i |\phi_i\rangle$$

Thus, $\phi_i' = c_i \phi_i$ corresponds to the projection of ϕ_i on i -axis in the holonomic space, and $|\psi\rangle$ corresponds to the external field in the holonomic space. The complex number c_i is the mapping of ϕ_i in the holonomic space, so the triangular relation about c_i :

$$\begin{cases} |c_1|^2 + |c_2|^2 = |q_1 b_1|^2 \\ |c_3|^2 + |q_1 b_1|^2 = |q_i b_i|^2 \\ |c_i|^2 + |q_i b_i|^2 = \|\psi\|^2 = \langle \psi | \psi \rangle \end{cases}$$

In $\lambda_i' = b_i \lambda_i$, λ_i is the intermediate state of the wave in the superposed sub-spaces. In the similar way of EQ07, zoom $|b_1|$ through the operation $|q_1 b_1|$ to satisfy the quadratic sum with $|c_i|$. Then the normalization equation at the larger flat local scale (holonomic space):

$$\sum |\psi|^2 dx = \sum_i |c_i|^2 = \sum_i P_i = 1$$

If $|c_i|^2$ is larger, the external field is stronger in the sub-space. Due to EQ03, $p_s = mv$ of the particle is smaller, and the position variation of the particle is smaller too, so the probability density to find the particle in the sub-space is higher. Hence the probability amplitude describes the rotation of the wave in the sub-space, and corresponds to the actual energy of the wave in the holonomic space.

In all, wave function in the form of complex number describes the gravitational interaction directly, and the quantum probability is not the random probability in maths, and it corresponds to the relative energy of the particle in the sub-space. Quantum mechanics is the real physical theory.

5.4 The Schrodinger equation is equivalent to field equation:

The classical wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} = v^2 \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2}$$

Let $y = \psi(x, t) = e^{ikx - i\omega t}$:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = e^{-i\omega t} \frac{\partial^2 e^{ikx}}{\partial x^2} = e^{-i\omega t} (ik)^2 e^{ikx} = -k^2 \psi$$

Due to 5.3.1, $k = p/\hbar$:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{m^2 v^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0 \quad (EQ5.4.1)$$

Due to EQ12 of the Hamiltonian of general relativity:

$$\mathcal{H} = T + V = mc^2$$

So:

$$\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = T = \mathcal{H} - V$$

Substitute in EQ5.4.1:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{m \cdot 2T}{\hbar^2} \psi = \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (\mathcal{H} - V) \psi = 0$$

Then:

$$\mathcal{H}\psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \cdot \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} + V\psi \quad (EQ5.4.2)$$

Since:

$$\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = e^{ikx} \cdot \frac{\partial e^{-i\omega t}}{\partial t} = -i\omega \cdot e^{-i\omega t} e^{ikx} = -i\omega\psi$$

Due to 5.3.2, $\omega = E/\hbar$:

$$\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = -i \cdot \frac{E}{\hbar} \psi = \frac{E}{i\hbar} \psi$$

Then:

$$E\psi = i\hbar \cdot \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t}$$

Since $E\psi = \mathcal{H}\psi$:

$$i\hbar \cdot \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} + V\psi \quad \dots\dots (EQ14)$$

EQ14 is just the Schrodinger equation derived from EQ12, so it is equivalent to the field equation of general relativity to describe the gravitational interaction as well.

5.5 The uncertainty principle is equivalent to space-time curvature:

The commutation relation in quantum mechanics is:

$$[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = \hat{x}\hat{p} - \hat{p}\hat{x} = i\hbar$$

Due to standard deviation equation:

$$\Delta A \cdot \Delta B \geq \frac{1}{2} |\langle [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] \rangle|$$

Then:

$$\Delta x \cdot \Delta p \geq \frac{1}{2} |\langle [\hat{x}, \hat{p}] \rangle| = \frac{1}{2} |\langle i\hbar \rangle|$$

So:

$$\Delta x \cdot \Delta p \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$$

This is Heisenberg's uncertainty principle in maths. The operators are for:

$$\hat{x}\phi_x(x) = x \cdot \phi_x(x) \quad ; \quad \hat{p}\phi_p(x) = p \cdot \phi_p(x)$$

Due to sections 3.6.1 and 4.4, $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar \neq 0$ means the coordinate systems of \hat{x} and \hat{p} are different. The effect of operators is to zoom the wave function in the direction in holonomic space in order to describe the interaction in the sub-space. \hbar applies for any wave, and i means the external field at any scale, so $i\hbar$ describes the angular momentum of a wave in any direction and at any scale.

Thus, \hat{x} or \hat{p} is for any wave function. Due to section 5.3, for:

$$\vec{X} = \vec{ds} \quad , \quad \vec{Y} = \vec{ds}_0$$

Due to section 3.6.1:

$$[\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] = E^2 - E_0^2 = E_s^2$$

Due to section 4.4:

$$\frac{1}{2}[\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] = E_k \cdot E$$

Since E is the energy of eigenstate:

$$\widehat{E}_k = E_k \cdot \phi$$

Thereby, the calculation of Lie bracket is equivalent to the operation in quantum mechanics. Since $[\widehat{x}, \widehat{p}]$ corresponds to angular momentum, due to EQ05 and EQ13:

$$\frac{1}{2}[\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] \cdot \Delta t_i = (E_k \cdot \Delta t_i) E = \left(\frac{1}{2} E_i \Delta t_i\right) E = \left(\frac{1}{2} \hbar\right) \cdot E$$

So:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{1}{2}[\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] \cdot \Delta t_i / E = \frac{1}{2} \hbar$$

Thus, $[\widehat{x}, \widehat{p}]$ describes the connection of the coordinate systems, and $\Delta x \Delta p$ describes the bending effect of two waves. The minimum uncertainty corresponds to the minimum bending effect at the larger flat local scale, and it describes the antisymmetry of the Poisson bracket as well. And the larger flat local scale is formed by the interaction of two waves in the stable outer external field of the outer flat space-time.

And about the quantum uncertainty, due to EQ13:

$$\hbar = \mathbf{p}_i x_i = \mathbf{p}_i \cdot \mathbf{c} \cdot \Delta t_i$$

If Δp is rather smaller, \mathbf{p}_i of \widehat{p} is smaller so that the measurement result is closer to $\langle \mathbf{p} \rangle$. And then Δt_i is larger for the wave \widehat{p} , so it takes rather longer time for the operation. Since $\Delta x = \mathbf{c} \cdot \Delta t_i$, if momentum is more certain, the position is more uncertain under the larger distance.

If Δx is rather smaller, Δt_i is smaller and it takes rather shorter time for the operation. Then \mathbf{p}_i of \widehat{p} is bigger, and so Δp is larger. Hence if the position is more certain, momentum is more uncertain.

Therefore, uncertainty principle is equivalent to the space-time curvature to describe the effect of gravitational interaction as general relativity.

5.6 The quantum path integral is equivalent to general relativity:

Due to EQ11, the Lagrangian in general relativity:

$$\mathcal{L} = T - V = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 - \frac{1}{2} m c^2 = -\frac{q}{2\gamma} m_0 c^2 = -\frac{q}{2\gamma} E_0$$

Thus, \mathcal{L} is the transformed form to describe the external field. When a particle moves from

point A to B at flat local scale, $Dx (A \rightarrow B)$ consists of many continuous dx along the path. The holonomic effect of the variable external field on the path is described by:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt (T - V) = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt (\mathcal{L})$$

Due to Fig.18 below, S describes the angular momentum of external wave on the path, then:

$$e^{ikx} = e^{ipx/\hbar} = e^{i(pc \cdot \Delta t)/\hbar} = e^{i(E \cdot \Delta t)/\hbar} = e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Thus, the external wave on each path corresponds to one wave function, so:

$$K_{ba} = \int D(x) e^{iS/\hbar}$$

This is the equation of quantum path integral. K_{ba} describes the holonomic external field on the path $Dx (A \rightarrow B)$. The physical meaning is that, the external field at the local scale is caused by the gravitational effect of countless particles in universe, and each path corresponds to one component caused by a portion of all particles. The external field is just the gravitational field where target particle moves, so K_{ba} is equivalent to $G_{\mu\nu}$ to describe space-time curvature.

Fig.18. quantum path integral describes the holonomy of external field on the path .

For example, in double slits interference experiment, the external field of target particle is caused by all the other particles in universe at the local scale. The particles forming two slits have the greatest contribution to the holonomic external field, so that K_{ba} is affected by the wave functions corresponding to the two slits. Thereby, the path of each particle is decided by the holonomic external field, and not restrained by the single slit. Thus, only one particle to pass the double slits can cause the interference effect. Of course, the extra field at local scale can change the holonomic external field. In the macro world, the external field of a heavy body is so stable at the larger local scale that the interference effect is too slight in the larger time interval Δt_i .

5.7 The physical significance of Dirac equation:

5.7.1 Another mathematical form of Dirac equation:

Due to EQ04 :

$$E^2 - E_s^2 = E_0^2$$

Then:

$$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$$

The first power form is supposed to be:

$$E = (\alpha_x p_x c + \alpha_y p_y c + \alpha_z p_z c) + \beta m_0 c^2$$

Multiply wave function ψ at both sides:

$$E\psi = (\alpha_x p_x c + \alpha_y p_y c + \alpha_z p_z c + \beta m_0 c^2)\psi$$

Due to section 5.4, $E\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$, $p = -i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}$:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -i\hbar c \alpha_x \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} - i\hbar c \alpha_y \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} - i\hbar c \alpha_z \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} + \beta m_0 c^2 \psi$$

Let $\alpha = (\alpha_x, \alpha_y, \alpha_z)$, $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = (\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z})$, then:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -i\hbar c \alpha \cdot \nabla \psi + \beta m_0 c^2 \psi$$

This is the Dirac equation to describe the gravitational interaction in the mixed form of wave function and special relativity at flat local scale. The matrix solution of Dirac equation is not very intuitive to understand the physical mechanism. I make another mathematical form due to EQ04:

$$m^2 c^4 = m^2 v^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$$

Divided by $m c^2$ on both sides:

$$m c^2 = m v^2 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot m_0 c^2$$

Let $v = v c / c$:

$$m c^2 = p c \cdot \frac{v}{c} + \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot m_0 c^2$$

Let $\kappa = \pm 1$, $\alpha = \pm \frac{v}{c}$, $\beta = \pm \frac{1}{\gamma}$:

$$\kappa E = \alpha \cdot E_s + \beta \cdot E_0$$

Since $\gamma = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}$:

$$\alpha^2 + \beta^2 = \left(\pm \frac{v}{c}\right)^2 + \left(\pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}\right)^2 = 1$$

So :

$$\begin{cases} \kappa E = \alpha E_s + \beta E_0 \\ \alpha^2 + \beta^2 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (\kappa = \pm 1, \kappa \beta \geq 0) \quad \dots\dots (EQ15)$$

EQ15 is another form of Dirac equation to describe the spin quantum state intuitively.

5.7.2 The physical significance of spin quantum state:

Fig.19. the spin quantum state .

Refer to Fig.19 (left), due to EQ15, $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 = 1$ describes a circle in geometry, and:

$$\alpha = \cos \theta , \beta = \sin \theta$$

Let axis- α be the real axis- R , and let axis- β be the imaginary axis- i . Then EQ15 holds on the complex plane, and the solution is just the wave function:

$$\psi = e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta$$

Thereby, the normalized wave functions on the entire complex plane are the solution of EQ15. Then there are following quantum states of the elementary particles:

1) The bosons:

In EQ15, when $\alpha = \pm 1$, $\beta = 0$, $v = c$:

$$\pm E = \pm E_s = \pm mvc = \pm mc^2$$

Refer to Fig.19 (right), the gravitational interaction in Dirac equation is considered as the vibration of matter wave with the variation of external field. The external field can be stronger or weaker than internal field at local scale, so the signs \pm of κ , α , β describe the wave direction is inward or outward the target particle. Energies are only positive, and the wave directions can be opposite.

$\beta = 0$ means $\cos \theta = 0$, so internal and external waves satisfy:

$$\vec{ds}_0 \perp \vec{ds}$$

Based on section 3.7, it is the condition of the maximum bending effect, so there is no gravitational interaction between the particle and external field at local scale. This situation is called that the static mass of the particle is zero, but in fact, the mass must not be zero in any condition, and this state of the particle describes the external field does not work on the particle,

and the particle is in the inertial reference frame in this condition. The particles in this condition are called the bosons.

Obviously, when the wave direction of boson spins one circle from + to – and back to + , the wave returns to the original state, so the spin quantum number of a boson is:

$$s = 1$$

And the angular momentum projection of a boson:

$$m_s = -1, 0, +1$$

Besides, when $\alpha = 0$, $\pm E = \pm E_0$. It corresponds to $m_s = 0$.

2) The fermions:

When $\alpha \neq 0$ & $\beta \neq 0$, $0 < v < c$. The particle has the matter wave:

$$\pm E_s = \pm mvc$$

The particle has relative speed at local scale in this condition: $E_k > 0$ or $p_s > 0$. Based on sections 5.4 and 5.5, angular momentum projection of matter wave is $\frac{1}{2}\hbar$ for the particle with E_k at flat local scale. Hence the particles are called the fermions with:

$$s = \frac{1}{2} ; m_s = -\frac{1}{2}, +\frac{1}{2}$$

Refer to Fig.19, when $\kappa = 1$, $\beta > 0$, $\alpha > 0$. The direction of matter wave is on the positive direction of R -axis, and it can be defined as spin down to describe inward direction.

When $\kappa = -1$, $\beta < 0$, $\alpha < 0$. The direction of matter wave is on the negative direction of R -axis, and it can be defined as spin up to describe outward direction.

Thereby, the fermion has two quantum states at flat local scale:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|\uparrow\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|\downarrow\rangle$$

Hence the quantum spin describes the spin of internal and external waves. When the two waves return to the original directions, the particle spins for a circle.

5.7.3 Anti-particle is the inverse quantum state at local scale:

Refer to below Fig.19 (left), there are four basic quantum states at local scale. If two particles have the same momentum p , $u^1(p)$ and $v^2(p)$ are the anti-particles of each other, and $u^2(p)$ and $v^1(p)$ are the anti-particles of each other, under the corresponding κ, α, β of each state.

Refer to Fig.20 (left), the directions of internal wave, external wave and matter wave are all

opposite between the pair of anti-particles. Due to EQ15, for the particle:

$$\kappa E = \alpha \cdot E_s + \beta \cdot E_0$$

Fig.20. quantum state of anti-particle .

For its anti-particle:

$$\kappa \rightarrow -\kappa, \alpha \rightarrow -\alpha, \beta \rightarrow -\beta$$

Then:

$$(-\kappa E) = (-\alpha \cdot E_s) + (-\beta \cdot E_0)$$

For the particle, if:

$$E > E_0$$

Then for its anti-particle:

$$-E > -E_0$$

So:

$$E < E_0$$

Hence the strength relationship between internal field and external field of the pair of anti-particles is reversed as:

$$e^{i\theta} \leftrightarrow e^{-i\theta}$$

It is same with the solution of Dirac equation for anti-particles:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_1^p &= u_1 e^{i/\hbar(px-Et)} \leftrightarrow \psi_1^a = v_1 e^{-i/\hbar(px-Et)} \\ \psi_2^p &= u_2 e^{i/\hbar(px-Et)} \leftrightarrow \psi_2^a = v_2 e^{-i/\hbar(px-Et)} \end{aligned}$$

Refer to Fig.20 (right), only matter wave at local scale can be observed, so the quantum state of anti-particle is actually the state of matter wave at the observation scale. Anti-particle is the state that the internal and external fields exchange with each other at the observation scale by increasing the energy density of the corresponding field. Thus, the inside part of anti-particle is the normal particle at the smaller scale, so anti-particle is the inverse state of matter wave at local scale.

5.8 Graviton is a pair of bosons:

Fig.21. the quantum state of graviton.

The metric tensor of general relativity has the form with components:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} + \kappa h_{\mu\nu}$$

$h_{\mu\nu}$ is the graviton field to describe the gravitational field caused by the extra objects in the existing field. Based on chapter 3, the gravitational field at any flat local scale is caused by a pair of virtual particles as internal wave and external wave. Internal and external waves can be considered as the matter waves at the smaller scale. Due to 5.7.2, internal and external waves are the bosons in their respective systems, so a pair of bosons is just the graviton.

Refer to Fig.21, due to FQ15, the state of the graviton:

$$E(1,0) = mc^2 \quad ; \quad E_0(0,1) = m_0c^2$$

Due to EQ15, the state of graviton:

$$E = |\alpha| E_s + |\beta| E_0$$

The graviton spins half-circle:

$$E'(-1,0) = -mc^2 \quad ; \quad E'_0(0,-1) = -m_0c^2$$

Then the state:

$$-E = (-|\alpha| E_s) + (-|\beta| E_0)$$

So:

$$E = |\alpha| E_s + |\beta| E_0$$

Thus, the graviton spins half-circle to return to the original state with:

$$s = 2 \quad ; \quad m_s = -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$$

In all, quantum mechanics is equivalent to general relativity to describe the gravitational

interaction.

6. The quantization theory of gravitation.

6.1 Spin quantum state corresponds to generalized electric charge:

6.1.1 The gravitational field describes the electric field:

Refer to Fig.22 (left) below, based on section 3.7, in the outer flat scale:

$$[\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] = E^2 - E_0^2 = E_s^2 = (\mathbf{p}_s c)^2 = (m v c)^2$$

Lie bracket is equal to vector outer product in three-dimensional sub-space. Corresponding the electromagnetic field, if external field is magnetic field:

$$\|\vec{B}\| = B = p_0 = m_0 c$$

Then gravitational field is the electric field by $\vec{E} \perp \vec{B}$:

$$\|\vec{E}\| = E = \gamma \cdot B v = \gamma m_0 c v = m v c = p_s c = E_s$$

Thus, the graviton field (composed by internal and external fields) describes the generalized electric field of a particle. Meanwhile, the external field is just the magnetic field of a particle.

Fig.22. the graviton field describes the generalized electric field.

Refer to Fig.22 (right), when a photon moves at flat local scale, $\vec{E} \perp \vec{B}$ in each Δt_i . Due to EQ05, the energy of matter wave in external field is equal to Poincare’s result:

$$E_{EM} = E_i = m v^2 = m c_i^2 = p_s \cdot c_i$$

When the electromagnetic wave \vec{ds} moves in the vacuum, there is the maximum bending effect between electromagnetic wave (matter wave) and external wave \vec{ds}_0 :

$$\vec{ds} \perp \vec{ds}_0 \quad , \quad \cos \theta = 0$$

Then for electromagnetic wave:

$$E_{EM} = E_i = m c_i^2$$

Thus, $E_k = 0$ for the bosons at flat local scale, and it does not matter with static mass.

Since $\overrightarrow{ds_s}$ describes $\overrightarrow{p_s}$, and $\overrightarrow{ds_0}$ describes \overrightarrow{r} , and let $m_0 = 1$, $dt_0 = 1$ in maths:

$$\overrightarrow{L} = \overrightarrow{p_s} \times \overrightarrow{r} \leftrightarrow \overrightarrow{E} = \overrightarrow{p_s} \times \overrightarrow{B} = \gamma (\overrightarrow{v} \times \overrightarrow{c})$$

Hence \overrightarrow{E} describes the spin angular momentum of a particle, and spin up and spin down corresponds to the direction of electric charge. Then the photon has no charge at the larger flat scale, but it has the generalized electric charge at the smaller curved scale, so does the atom.

6.1.2 Lagrangian of electromagnetic field describes the external field at the outer scale:

The Lagrangian of electromagnetic field in *QED* :

$$\mathcal{L}_{EM} = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} (B^2 - \frac{E^2}{c^2})$$

Since $E = \gamma B v = \gamma B c_i$, $c = c_i$ for local scale:

$$\mathcal{L}_{EM} = \frac{1}{2} (B^2 - \frac{\gamma^2 B^2 c_i^2}{c_i^2}) = \frac{1}{2} B^2 (1 - \gamma^2)$$

Since $B = p_0 = m_0 c$, $c_i = v$ for γ :

$$\mathcal{L}_{EM} = -\frac{1}{2} m_0^2 c^2 \frac{v^2}{c^2 - v^2} = -\frac{1}{2} m_0^2 v^2 \gamma^2 = -\frac{1}{2} m^2 v^2 = -\frac{1}{2} p_s^2$$

Due to section 5.5:

$$\mathcal{L}_{EM} \cdot c^2 = -\frac{1}{2} m^2 v^2 c^2 = -\frac{1}{2} E_s^2 = -\frac{1}{2} [\nabla_{\vec{x}}, \nabla_{\vec{y}}] = \left(-\frac{1}{2} \hbar\right) \cdot \left(\frac{E}{\Delta t_i}\right)$$

Thus, although \mathcal{L}_{EM} has the mathematical form about momentum, $\mathcal{L}_{EM} \cdot c^2$ actually describes the antisymmetry of the generator (graviton). Thereby, \mathcal{L}_{EM} describes the external field outside to balance the matter wave. Moreover, in the non-inertial reference frame outside the matter wave, A_μ in \mathcal{L}_{EM} describes the variation of external field as the virtual photon to propagate electromagnetic force in *QED* .

6.1.3 Generalized electric charge corresponds to spin quantum state at local scale:

Due to Gauss's law for the flat local scale:

$$E = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \frac{Q}{4\pi r^2}$$

Since $\frac{1}{c_i^2} = \epsilon_0 \mu_0$:

$$E = \mu_0 c^2 \frac{Q}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{\mu_0 (Q c_i)}{4\pi r^2} \cdot c_i$$

Since $E = B v = B c_i$:

$$B c_i = \frac{\mu_0 (Q c_i)}{4\pi r^2} \cdot c_i$$

Due to EQ01: $\mu_0 = 4\pi G$, EQ02: $M = qv = Q c_i$:

$$B = \frac{4\pi GM}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{GM}{r^2} = g_i$$

Hence electromagnetic field is equivalent to gravitational field at each local scale. The electromagnetic field in the vacuum on earth describes the gravitational interaction at just one local scale. Since $dt = 1$, $m_0 = 1$ for simplified calculation in maths, the acceleration:

$$g_i = a = \frac{F}{m_0} = \frac{dp}{dt} \frac{1}{m_0} = \frac{p_0}{dt} \frac{1}{m_0} = \frac{B}{dt} \frac{1}{m_0} = B$$

Thus, the formulas about B in this section are consistent in maths.

Refer to Fig.23 below, the measurement subject is the matter wave of the particle. In Δt_i of the observation scale, if wave direction is inward, the particle has negative charge at local scale; if wave direction is outward, the particle has positive charge at local scale; if it is symmetric in the opposite directions, the particle has no charge at local scale.

Based on section 6.1.1, electric field describes the angular momentum of magnetic field and momentum. In the similar way, magnetic field also describes the angular momentum of electric field and momentum in maths. Thus, the magnetic moment just describes generalized electric charge at local scale. The electric and the magnetic are equivalent according to relativity.

Fig.23. the generalized electric charges.

Especially, at the macro scale on earth, the electron has negative charge for 100%:

$$|\psi\rangle = 1 |\downarrow\rangle$$

The proton has positive charge for 100%:

$$|\psi\rangle = 1 |\uparrow\rangle$$

Thus, the spin quantum states depend on the observation scale and the energy density of external field, and spin direction corresponds to the generalized charge of particle at the corresponding local scale. Thereby, the electron and proton attract each other sometimes, and repel each other sometimes at the corresponding local scale, because the generalized charges of them are variable. It is not scientific to use the macro-scale state to define the micro-scale state

of a particle in the different external fields. And so electrons do not fall into the atomic nucleus.

In all, electric field is the state of matter wave in external field, and electromagnetic field is caused by the gravitational interaction at local scale as the position of target particle changes relatively. Electric field describes the gravitational field of the target particle, and magnetic field describes the gravitational field of all the other matters as the external field at local scale. Hence electric field has the divergence centered on a particle, and magnetic field has no divergence because external field is not caused from the fixed position.

6.2 The gravitization law of quantum:

Due the Lorentz force in the uniform magnetic field as the flat space-time:

$$\mathbf{F} = q\mathbf{v}\mathbf{B}$$

Due to Biot-Savart Law: $\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{qv}{r^2}$:

$$\mathbf{F} = (qv) \cdot \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{(QV)}{r^2}$$

Due to EQ01: $\mu_0 = 4\pi G$, EQ02: $m = qv$:

$$\mathbf{F} = (m) \cdot \frac{4\pi G}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{(M)}{r^2} = \frac{GMm}{r^2}$$

Thus, Lorentz force is equivalent to Newton's law in flat space-time. Due to EQ13:

$$\hbar = \mathbf{E}_i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{t}_i = m_i c^2 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{t}_i$$

Gravitation in flat space-time:

$$F_{G-flat} = \frac{GMm}{r^2} = \frac{G}{r^2} \cdot \frac{\hbar}{c^2 dT} \cdot \frac{\hbar}{c^2 dt} = \frac{1}{r^2 \cdot dT \cdot dt} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4}$$

Let $r^2 = n \cdot dr^2$, $dt_0 = n \cdot dT$:

$$F_{G-flat} = \frac{1}{dr^2 \cdot n \cdot dT \cdot dt} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4} = \frac{1}{dr^2 \cdot dt_0 \cdot dt} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4}$$

dT corresponds to the matter wave of object M , and dt corresponds to the matter wave of object m in the vacuum. $dt_0 = n \cdot dT$ corresponds to the matter wave of M at the distance r . $dr^2 = r^2/n$ is used to simplify the mathematical form.

In curved space-time, due to EQ08: $dt_0 = q\gamma \cdot dt$:

$$F_G = \frac{1}{dr^2 \cdot q\gamma \cdot dt^2} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4} = \frac{1}{dr^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4 \cdot dt^2}$$

Let $dr^2 = c^2 \cdot \Delta t_r^2$, $q \cdot \Delta t_r^2 = \Delta t^2$:

$$F_G = \frac{1}{c^2 \cdot \Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{c^4 \cdot dt^2} = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6}$$

Let $Q = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma}$, $C = \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6}$:

$$\begin{cases} F_G = Q \cdot C \\ Q = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} ; C = \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6} \end{cases} \dots\dots (EQ16)$$

EQ16 is the law of the gravitationalization of quantum. C describes the constant construct of gravitational interaction, and Q describes the variable construct to explain the space-time curvature. Δt describes the time for light wave to pass the distance dr at local scale. The scale is flatter when Δt is smaller, and it is more curved when Δt is larger. \hbar, c, G, dt can be considered as the unit 1 at local scale for the constant condition.

Especially, Lorentz factor γ in EQ16 has below forms:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} & (\text{for target particle}) \\ \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} & (\text{for gravitational field}) \end{cases}$$

With the condition:

$$0 \leq v \left(\sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}} \right) \leq c$$

In the form of $1/\gamma$ in EQ16, the gravitation has no the infinite problem with the clear condition. γ and Δt are decided by the time, so the interaction of the quantum can be described by the time in the form of gravitational force. Hence EQ16 is the unified law of relativistic gravitation and quantum mechanics in the form of gravitational force.

6.3 Explain the physical effects according to the unified law:

6.3.1 Opposite poles attract and like poles repel:

Fig.24. opposite poles attract .

Refer to Fig.23 (left), when a neutral particle m_1 is in the inertial reference frame, its charge $Q = 0$, and the external force in any direction:

$$\Delta F = F_1 - F_2 = 0$$

Refer to Fig.23 (right), when another neutral particle m_2 moves in the field of m_1 , according to general relativity, m_2 decreases the gravitational field of m_1 at the position. Thus, F_2 decreases in the direction of m_2 , and:

$$\Delta F = F_1 - F_2 = F_G > 0$$

Hence F_G between two objects is caused by the change of external field for each object. m_2 spins down to have negative charge at local scale because of its gravitational field. The gravitational field of m_1 decreases at the position, so it spins up to the opposite direction at the local scale to have positive charge there. Thus, they attract each other as the opposite poles, and electromagnetic interaction is caused by gravitational interaction.

Refer to Fig.24 (left) below, when two positive charges are in the field of the other one, they spin up at local scale to decrease external field of each other, and F_2 increases in the direction:

$$\Delta F = F_1 - F_2 = F_G < 0$$

Refer to Fig.24 (right) below, when two negative charges are in the field of the other one, they spin down at local scale to increase external field of each other, and F_2 increases in the direction too. Hence like poles repel each other under $F_G < 0$, meanwhile the attractive effect occurs in the opposite direction for each one.

Fig.25. like poles repel.

Obviously, quantum entanglement is caused by opposite poles attract based on gravitational interaction. It occurs at the smaller scale than the light wave scale on earth, so it is possible to be faster than light speed.

6.3.2 The elliptical orbit of celestial bodies:

Fig.26. the reason of elliptical orbit .

Refer to Fig.26 (left), celestial body m orbits around M_1 . Due to EQ04, m is faster when external field is weaker, and it is slower when external field is stronger at the holonomic scale, so the external field at the outer scale (outside the system of m and M_1) must affect the motion and orbit of m . The external field at the outer scale is supposed to be the gravitational field of M_2 as the mass of the matter group system outside, and $M_1 < M_2$.

m is in the gravitational field of M_1 , so M_1 always spins down with negative charge at the local scale at the position of m , and M_2 always spins up with positive charge at the local scale. When m is the closest to M_2 , the external field of m is the strongest, so m spins up with positive charge at local scale, and then m and M_2 repel each other by like charges, meanwhile m and M_1 attract each other by opposite charges. The gravitation on m is:

$$F_G = F_1 - F_2 > 0$$

Refer to Fig.26 (right), when m is the closest to M_1 , external field of m is the weakest, so m spins down with negative charge at the local scale. Then m and M_1 repel each other by like charges, meanwhile m and M_2 attract each other by opposite charges. The gravitation:

$$F_G = F_1 - F_2 < 0$$

Thus, when m moves around M_1 , the external field of m is variable all the time, and it is attracted and repelled by M_1 periodically, so that the orbits of the celestial bodies do not respect the centripetal force model actually in physics, and the orbits are always elliptical. Of course, energy conservation still works between M_1 and m .

Moreover, the gravitational field of a heavy body at each position in the space is affected by the other bodies in universe. Any kind of Newton's law in the flat space-time can not explain the actual gravitational field at a position in the complex environment. For example, the position

closer to the center or at the edge of the galaxy has the stronger gravitational field than calculation because the gravitational field of other heavy bodies outside is even weaker there. The dark matter caused by Newton's law can not be trusted, and only general relativity can explain the gravitation in the actual curved space-time.

6.3.3 The light bending and red-shift effects:

1) The light bending effect:

Refer to Fig.27 below, when light wave moves closer to the heavy body M , the external field of light wave increases, and light wave is curved from \overline{AB} to \overline{AC} in dt to take more time to pass the original distance $|\overline{AB}|$ according to general relativity. Due to EQ16, the coefficient:

$$Q = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} = \frac{1}{\Delta t_r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma}$$

For gravitational field:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}$$

Fig.27. light bending effect.

Then:

$$Q^2 = \frac{1}{\Delta t_r^4 \cdot q^2 \gamma^2} = \frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta t_r^4}$$

So:

$$Q^2 \cdot \Delta t_r^4 = \frac{1}{q^2} \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) = -g_{00}$$

Hence there is g_{00} of EQ10 derived from EQ16, so the unified law is equivalent to field equation of general relativity.

2) The relativistic Doppler redshift effect:

Fig.28. red-shift effect .

Refer to Fig.28, in Relativistic Doppler redshift effect, for the static observer M , $v = 0$.
Due to EQ16, the gravitation on the photon is:

$$F_{G-static} = Q \cdot C = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G \hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot \frac{G \hbar^2}{\Delta t^2 dt^2 c^6} = \frac{G \hbar^2}{\Delta t^2 dt^2 c^6}$$

Then for the moving M , if $v \ll c$, the taylor expansion:

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} \approx 1 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v^2}{c^2}$$

The gravitation on the photon:

$$F_{G-motion} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot \frac{G \hbar^2}{\Delta t^2 dt^2 c^6} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \cdot F_{G-static} = F_{G-static} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v^2}{c^2} F_{G-static}$$

So:

$$\Delta F_G = F_{G-static} - F_{G-motion} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v^2}{c^2} F_{G-static}$$

$$\Delta F_G = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} F_{G-static} \quad (EQ6.3.3)$$

Let $c = c_i$ for the propagation speed in the vacuum, and it is considered that the photon makes uniform circular motion at the smaller local scale at the speed c , then for the photon:

$$F_G = \frac{mc^2}{r}$$

Substitute into EQ6.3.3:

$$\frac{\Delta mc^2}{r} = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{mc^2}{r}\right)$$

Multiply mc_i^2 at both sides, due to EQ06:

$$\Delta mc_i^2 mc^2 = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} m^2 c_i^2 c^2\right) = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} E_s^2 = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot E_s'^2$$

Let $\Delta mc_i^2 mc^2 = (\Delta E_s')^2$:

$$(\Delta E_s')^2 = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \cdot E_s'^2$$

Then:

$$\Delta E_s' = \frac{v}{c} \cdot E_s'$$

Due to EQ13, $E = hf$:

$$h \cdot |\Delta f| = \frac{v}{c} \cdot (hf)$$

So:

$$\frac{|\Delta f|}{f} = \frac{v}{c}$$

Finally, the same Relativistic Doppler red-shift equation in the condition of $v \ll c$ is derived from EQ16.

3) The gravitational redshift:

Due to EQ6.3.3:

$$\Delta F_G = \frac{v^2}{c_i^2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} F_{G-static}$$

Due to EQ16:

$$\frac{\Delta F_G}{F_{G-static}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{v^2}{c_i^2} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{2GM}{rc_i^2} = \frac{GM}{rc_i^2}$$

In the similar way:

$$\frac{\Delta F_G}{F_{G-static}} = \frac{\Delta mc^2/r}{mc^2/r} = \frac{\Delta E}{E} = \frac{h|\Delta f|}{hf} = \frac{|\Delta f|}{f}$$

Let $c_i = c$ for general form:

$$\frac{|\Delta f|}{f} = \frac{GM}{rc^2}$$

Thus, the same gravitational redshift equation is derived from EQ16 as well. The unified law can also describes the motion and variation of the quantum, and the red/blue-shift effect is actually caused by the variation of the gravitational field where the photon is.

Moreover, the cosmic redshift effect has another explanation that, our solar system is moving into the weaker field in the galaxy and then the gravitational field of our solar system is getting stronger relatively in this period. Hence all the light waves entering our solar system in this period have the red-shift effect in the stronger field. Of course, the cosmic expansion at the observation scale is one of the possible reasons. But dark energy can not be trusted.

6.3.4 The time delay effect between the satellite and the ground:

There is the time delay effect between in the satellite and on the ground. The correction of general relativity is:

$$\Delta t_{GR} \approx \frac{GM}{c^2} \left(\frac{1}{r_{earth}} - \frac{1}{r_{sat}} \right) \approx 45 \mu s/day$$

It is said the correction of special relativity is:

$$\Delta t_{SR} \approx -\frac{v^2}{2c^2} \approx -7 \mu s/day$$

But in fact, special relativity describes the space-time curvature effect in inertial reference frame, and general relativity describes the space-time curvature effect in non-inertial reference frame. Thus, The two theories can not calculate the same effect together. Due to EQ16:

$$-\frac{v^2}{2c^2} = -\frac{2GM_{sat}}{2rc^2} = -\frac{GM_{sat}}{rc^2}$$

So:

$$\Delta t_{SR} = \Delta t_{GR-sat} = -\frac{GM_{sat}}{rc^2} = -\frac{|\Delta f_{wave-sat}|}{f_{wave-sat}}$$

Thus, the correction of special relativity is actually the correction of the gravitational field of the satellite, and the correction of general relativity is actually the correction of the gravitational field of the earth. So the total time delay:

$$\Delta t = \Delta t_{GR} + \Delta t_{SR} = \Delta t_{GR-earth} + \Delta t_{GR-sat} \approx 38 \mu s/day$$

Thereby, the time delay effect is actually caused by the different frequencies of the waves on earth and in the satellite. It does not matter with special relativity, and the real proper time does not change with the speed or gravitational field.

6.4 Explain the strong interaction according to the unified law:

6.4.1 Colour charge conservation describes electromagnetic shielding:

Refer to Fig.28 (left) below, the proton’s charge is considered as contributing of three quarks only:

$$Q_p = Q_u + Q_u + Q_d = \left(+\frac{2}{3}e\right) + \left(+\frac{2}{3}e\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{3}e\right) = +e$$

Fig.29. colour charge conservation of proton .

According to Gauss’s theorem, if the changes in the system can be directly added together, the charges of three quarks are actually the effects distributed on the surface, and the internal electric field is zero. Then the equipotential surface of the proton:

$$\varphi(r) = \text{constant}$$

A is any point at the equipotential surface, and the gravitational force on **A** caused by the three quarks and propagated by the internal gluon field A_μ^a is:

$$F_{G-in} = \sum F_i$$

Due to EQ16, the coefficient of F_G :

$$Q = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} , \quad C = \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6}$$

$\Delta t = \text{constant}$ and $1/\gamma = \text{constant}$ at the constant equipotential surface. Then only dt_i is the variable of F_i between each pair of quarks. Due to EQ13:

$$\hbar = m_i c^2 \cdot \Delta t_i = m_i c_i^2 \cdot dt_i$$

Due to EQ02, $m = qv = qc_i$ at equipotential surface, so:

$$m \propto q$$

Then:

$$\frac{1}{dt_i^2} = \frac{m_i^2 c_i^4}{\hbar^2} \propto q_i^2$$

Let C_0 correspond to $q = +e$:

$$F_i = \pm q_i^2 \cdot QC_0$$

So:

$$F_{G-in} = \sum F_i = \left(\frac{4}{9} - \frac{4}{9} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{9} + \frac{4}{9} - \frac{4}{9} \right) QC_0 = 0$$

Hence $F_{G-in} = 0$ is equivalent to $E_{in} = 0$ for electromagnetic shielding effect, that is the physical significance of colour conservation. QCD actually describes the symmetry of the matter group system and the external field. Let $\overrightarrow{ds_{in}}$ be the result of internal interaction to describe the gluon field, and it is on the equipotential surface and in the null-space of its external field by:

$$\overrightarrow{ds_{in}} \perp \overrightarrow{ds_s}$$

Refer to Fig.28 (right), when quarks and gluons are variable to be the different sub-groups along the time, $F_{G-in} = 0$ at equipotential surface always, so the matter wave and electric field of a proton in external field does not change all the time.

Fig.30. colour charge conservation of neutron .

Refer to Fig.29, the neutron's charge is considered as contributing of three quarks:

$$Q_n = Q_u + Q_d + Q_d = \left(+\frac{2}{3}e\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{3}e\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{3}e\right) = 0 (e)$$

In a similar way, the internal gravitational force on A at equipotential surface:

$$F_{G-in} = \sum F_i = \left(\frac{4}{9} - \frac{4}{9} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{9}\right) Q C_0 = 0$$

Refer to Fig.31 below, each particle is a stable matter group system at the flat local scale, and $SU(3)$ is only one of the mathematical solutions of the stable system. Each quark with the basic colour is supposed to be a dimension to cause the virtual waves inside the system, and gluons are supposed to be the combination of the virtual waves in order to offset each other's momentums at equipotential surface. That is described by Yang-Mills equation:

$$\partial^\mu F_{\mu\nu}^a + g_s f^{abc} A_b^\mu F_{\mu\nu}^c = 0$$

Thus, gluons are like the internal and external waves in relativity to describe the gauge field caused by the material field. The material field is caused by the matter group systems with higher energy density to generate the gravitation, and the gauge field is caused by the matter group systems with lower energy density to propagate the gravitation at the flat local scale.

Fig.31. any particle is a matter group system .

The three quarks have the specific charges, but the matters in the system change positions always and quarks can not be made up of the same matters along the time. Thereby, each quark is just the temporary sub-group in each Δt in order to correspond to the specific charge, so that the life of the quark is very short, and the matters to make up the quark are always different.

6.4.2 Asymptotic Freedom is the effect of gravitation:

Due to EQ16, the gravitational force between two quarks are:

$$F_G = Q \cdot C = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2 \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6} = \frac{1}{\Delta t_r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^6} = \frac{1}{dr^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^4} = \frac{n}{r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^4}$$

The variable part of F_G is:

$$f(r) = \frac{n}{r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left[r^{-2} \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{1/2} \right]$$

At the local scale:

$$\frac{df}{dr} = \frac{n}{q} \left[\left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{1/2} \cdot \frac{d}{dr} r^{-2} + r^{-2} \cdot \frac{d}{dr} \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{1/2} \right] = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1/2} \cdot r^{-4} \cdot \left(-2r + \frac{5r_s}{2}\right)$$

When two quarks are closer:

$$dr < 0$$

If F_G decreases for asymptotic freedom:

$$dF_G < 0 \rightarrow df < 0$$

Then:

$$\frac{df}{dr} > 0$$

Since the other items are positive:

$$-2r + \frac{5r_s}{2} > 0$$

So:

$$r_s < r < \frac{5}{4}r_s$$

Thus, F_G decreases in above condition, that describes the effect of Asymptotic Freedom as well. Moreover, when $r \leq r_s$, $F_G = 0$. In this condition, the particle is inside the boundary to become a part of the system. Hence the stable black hole is also a matter group system under the same mechanism of strong interaction, so is the ball lightning at flat local scale.

6.4.3 Quark Confinement is the effect of gravitation:

According to section 6.4.2, the gravitational force on the quark inside the hadron:

$$F_G = QC = \frac{n}{r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} \cdot \frac{G\hbar^2}{dt^2 c^4}$$

Let:

$$f(r, v) = \frac{n}{r^2 \cdot q \cdot \gamma} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right)$$

Since $v = v(r)$:

$$\frac{df}{dr} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left[\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{d}{dr} r^{-2}\right) + r^{-2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{1/2} \right] = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left(-\frac{2}{r^3} \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} - \frac{dv}{dr} \cdot \frac{v}{c^2 r^2} \cdot \gamma\right)$$

The relation of v and r in gravitational field :

$$\frac{dv}{dr} < 0$$

Then:

$$\frac{df}{dr} = \frac{n}{q} \cdot \left(-\frac{2}{r^3} \frac{1}{\gamma} + \left|\frac{dv}{dr}\right| \cdot \frac{v}{c^2 r^2} \cdot \gamma\right)$$

If the quark can not escape from the boundary, when $dr > 0$, $dF_G > 0$ somewhere. So:

$$\frac{df}{dr} > 0$$

Then:

$$-\frac{2}{r^3} \frac{1}{\gamma} + \left|\frac{dv}{dr}\right| \cdot \frac{v}{c^2 r^2} \cdot \gamma > 0$$

So:

$$\left|\frac{dv}{dr}\right| > \frac{2c^2}{rv\gamma^2} \quad \text{..... (EQ17)}$$

EQ17 is the condition of quark confinement. It means if external field is strong enough to make quark's speed v decreases quickly, F_G from the hadron increases when the quark is closer to the boundary. Moreover, EQ17 also holds when $dr < 0$, $df < 0$, and F_G decreases when the quark is closer to the center, so the quarks do not collide with each other in a hadron.

In all, the physical mechanism of strong interaction describes the stable matter group system in the external field that is strong enough. The mechanism works both in the micro and macro scales in universe.

6.5 Explain the weak interaction according to the unified law:

6.5.1 The weak interaction is the effect of symmetry breaking:

According to section 6.4, strong interaction describes the symmetry of the stable matter group system in the strong external field. Then when external field is weak enough, the condition of symmetry breaking is opposite:

$$\left|\frac{dv}{dr}\right| < \frac{2c^2}{rv\gamma^2} \quad \text{..... (EQ18)}$$

Take β^- decay effect of neutron for instance. When external field becomes weaker to satisfy EQ18, some sub-group in the neutron escapes out of the boundary by:

The neutron has the material field $u - d - d$ before decay. After sub-group's escape, the remaining matters regroup the material field $u - u - d$ and the gluon field to become the proton. And W^- boson decays to be the electron in external field. Conversely, the β^+ decay effect:

$$p \rightarrow n + e^+ + \nu_e$$

$$p + e^- \rightarrow n + \nu_e$$

In fact, the decay effects describe the same physical mechanism that the sub-group escapes from the stronger field to the weaker field if EQ18 is satisfied, and become the negative charge in the weaker field.

The physical mechanism of weak interaction breaks the symmetry of strong interaction, and causes the material exchange between the matter group system and the external field. Obviously, all the kinds of escaping effects are caused by the same mechanism of weak interaction, such as radiation, photoelectric effect, black hole jet, etc.

6.5.2 The spin of neutrino is the spin of the field:

Refer to Fig.31 (up) below, when the sub-group escapes from neutron to the external field, according to general relativity and quantum mechanics, the sub-group with higher energy spins up in the weaker field to become the electron e^- . Relatively, the matter wave of external field spins down to become the anti-neutrino $\bar{\nu}_e$ for the balance.

Fig.32. the spin of neutrino .

Refer to Fig.32 (down), in the similar way, the sub-group with lower energy escapes from the proton and spins down in the stronger external field to become the anti-electron e^+ . Relatively, the matter wave of external field spins up to become the neutrino ν_e for the balance.

Therefore, the spin of the neutrino is actually the spin of the field. $\bar{\nu}_e$ spins down to have the generalized positive charge, so it is right-handed only; ν_e spins up to have the generalized negative charge, so it is left-handed only. The graviton field of e^+ or e^- causes the matter wave of external field to change in only one direction, thus, the neutrino has only one spin direction.

Additionally, about neutrino oscillation, just like the atomic nucleus, the neutrino is a matter group system at the much smaller scale as well. When neutrino groups move in variable external field, the sub-groups exchange between the neutrino groups to cause the different quantum states of neutrino.

6.5.3 Explain the physical effects under the mechanism of weak interaction:

1) Plunging infall into the black hole:

According to the mechanism of strong interaction, if matter group is stable, the sub-groups in it move in the orbits continuously. The black hole is a sub-group of a matter group too, so the other bodies in the system do not fall into black hole when the system is stable.

When some sub-group becomes stronger or the black hole becomes weaker, the matters in the sub-group will escape the boundary to fall into the black hole. The matters have rather faster speed v in the weaker external field, so they plunge into the black hole.

2) The mechanism of superconductivity:

Fig.33. the mechanism of superconductivity .

Refer to Fig.33, the conductor can be considered as a matter group system at the large scale, and each molecule is one sub-group. In the low temperature condition, the external field is weak enough to satisfy EQ18, and then the Cooper pair of electrons in each sub-group escapes out of the boundary and into the next sub-group.

The energy of only a pair of electrons can satisfy EQ18 for the escape effect in the very weak external field, but the small energy can not satisfy EQ18 in the stronger external field at the high temperature. The room-temperature condition on earth is fixed, so the solution is to increase the

energy of the sub-group. So the multi-electron group or ion-group with the high start-up energy is possible for high temperature superconductivity.

3) Physical changes and Chemical changes:

The physical changes and chemical changes describe the changes of matter groups at the different scales under the mechanisms of weak interaction and strong interaction. For example, the physical changes between a pair of photons and electron-positron pair are:

$$e^- + e^+ \leftrightarrow \gamma + \gamma$$

A photon or an electron is a stable matter group system as well. In the high energy external field, the gravitational field of each particle decrease quite a lot, so that the particles are much closer to each other. When EQ18 is satisfied between a pair of particles, the sub-group of one particle escapes to the other one. Then e^- loses energy to become the new stable state of γ , meanwhile e^+ gets energy to become γ ; conversely, γ loses energy to become the new stable state of e^+ , meanwhile the other γ gets energy to become e^- .

In all, weak interaction describes the mechanism of symmetry breaking, and the escaping effect occurs at the smaller scale in a matter group system all the time.

6.6 The quantization law of gravitation:

6.6.1 Four-dimensional space-time complex coordinate system:

Fig.34. four-dimentional space-time complex coordinate system .

Refer to Fig.34, it is the schematic diagram of the four-dimentional space-time coordinate system in multi-scale space. The origin point is not a point of zero dimension, and it has the minimum time interval dt to describe external field. The coordinates on each axis describes the positions of the particle in external field. The imaginary number describes external field in wave

function, so origin point is $\mathbf{O} [dt(i), \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{0}]$ and basis vector is $\vec{e} [dt(i), x, y, z]$.

In the sub-spaces, the sub-external fields are variable because of space-time curvature. Due to EQ07, the connection of the sub-spaces is:

$$dt_i = q_i \cdot dt_{i-1}$$

So:

$$dt_n = (q_1 q_2 \cdots q_n) \cdot dt = dt \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n q_i \quad \dots\dots (EQ19)$$

EQ19 describes the connection of the minimum time intervals in each sub-space. Since $q_i > 1$, $dt_n \gg dt$. Thus, the macro world is more certain than the micro world because the measurement scale dt_i is too short for the macro world. And dt_i is the only variable for all the physical quantities in the form of four dimensional space-time coordinate system.

6.6.2 The law of quantization of gravitation:

Due to EQ07, the forms of metric in general relativity:

$$ds^2 = \begin{pmatrix} -dt_0^2 & dxdt_0 & dydt_0 & dzdt_0 \\ dt_0dx & dx^2 & dydx & dzdx \\ dt_0dy & dxdy & dy^2 & dzdy \\ dt_0dz & dxdz & dydz & dz^2 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow ds^2 = \begin{pmatrix} -dt_0^2/q^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & dx^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & dy^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & dz^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\rightarrow g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -1/q^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

From diagonal matrix $g_{\mu\nu}$, Let:

$$Q_i = \begin{pmatrix} 1/q_i^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} ; C = \begin{pmatrix} i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \pm 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \pm 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The Minkowski metric:

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = C^2 = \text{diag} (-1, 1, 1, 1) = Q_i^{-1} C^2 Q_i$$

Due to EQ19:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n Q_i = C^2 \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n Q_i$$

And the unitary transformation:

$$C^\dagger C = (C^*)^T C = C^* C = I$$

Let $\sum_n |c_n|^2 = 1$, then:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_n c_n \cdot C$$

And:

$$\int |\psi|^2 = \sum_n |c_n|^2 (C^* C) = \sum_n |c_n|^2 = 1$$

It is equivalent to Born's rule:

$$\langle \psi | \psi \rangle = \int |\psi|^2 dx = \sum_n |c_n|^2 = 1$$

Finally:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{Q}_i = \text{diag} (1/q_i^2, 1, 1, 1) \quad ; \quad \mathbf{C} = \text{diag} (i, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1) \\ \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i = \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i \quad ; \quad \eta_{\mu\nu} = \prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i \quad \dots\dots (\text{EQ20}) \\ \langle \psi | \psi \rangle = \int |\psi|^2 = \sum_n |c_n|^2 (C^* C) = \sum_n |c_n|^2 = 1 \end{array} \right.$$

EQ20 is the law of quantization of gravitaiton to unify the general relativity and quantum mechanics in the form of complex matrix in maths. \mathbf{C} describes the basis vector in the four dimensional coordinate system in each sub-space. $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ describes the flat local scale, and \mathbf{Q}_i describes the curved scale.

$\prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i^{-1}$ and $\prod_{i=1}^n \mathbf{Q}_i$ describe the external field of the matter group system becomes stronger or weaker, so it is equivalent to \mathcal{L}_{int} in QFT to describe the interaction of particles. Hence relativity and QFT are unified under EQ20 in maths.

6.6.3 The vacuum energy at local scale:

Take Ramanujan summation for instance:

$$c = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots + n = -\frac{1}{12}$$

Of course it is impossible for real number field. Let:

$$4c = 4 + 8 + 12 + \dots + 4n$$

Then:

$$c - 4c = 1 - 2 + 3 - 4 + \dots$$

In the form of matrix:

$$-3c = (1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 \dots)^2$$

Substitute $(i^2)^k$ in each item:

$$-3c = [(i^2)^0 + (i^2)^1 + (i^2)^2 + (i^2)^3 + \dots]^2$$

Let $s = i^2 = -1$:

$$-3c = (1 + s + s^2 + s^3 + \dots)^2$$

For the item:

$$b = 1 + s + s^2 + s^3 + \dots$$

Multiply s at both sides:

$$bs = s + s^2 + s^3 + s^4 \dots$$

So:

$$b - bs = 1$$

Then:

$$b = \frac{1}{1-s} = \frac{1}{1-(-1)} = \frac{1}{2}$$

Thus:

$$-3c = b^2 = \frac{1}{4}$$

Finally in complex number field:

$$c = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = -\frac{1}{12}$$

It is used in Riemann ζ function:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

when $s = i^2 = -1$:

$$\zeta(-1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = -\frac{1}{12}$$

$\zeta(-1)$ is used for Zero-point energy:

$$E_{vacuum} = \langle 0|H|0 \rangle = \sum_k \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$$

Fig.35. the vacuum energy at local scale .

Refer to Fig.35, at flat local scale, $\langle \psi | \psi \rangle = C^* C = 1$. The vector projection at real axis corresponds to E_s of matter wave, and vector projection at imaginary axis corresponds to E_0 of external wave. E_s increases as E_0 decreases, thus, the vacuum is the condition at local scale in maths:

$$E_s \rightarrow 1 \quad \& \quad E_0 \rightarrow 0$$

In $\zeta(s)$, $n^{-s} = (n^s)^{-1}$ to describe the inverse relation. $s = i^2$ corresponding to the time item in $\eta_{\mu\nu} = C^2$. There is the inverse relation of matter wave and external wave:

$$\frac{E_0}{E_s} = \left(\frac{E_s}{E_0}\right)^{-1}$$

Thus, the maximum convergence of E_s corresponds to the minimum convergence of E_0 , and $\zeta(i^2)$ corresponds to $E_{vac} = E_{0-min}$ at local scale. Hence vacuum describes the weakest external field at local scale, and each scale has its own vacuum light speed c_i .

6.6.4 The multi-scale space-time:

Refer to Fig.36 below, when the particles (objects) move closer to each other, the matters at the center have the pressure from outside. If EQ17 is satisfied, the matters at the center will form the new matter group system in the strong external field. Thus, each stable matter group system has the attraction to the field at local scale.

There are many scales inside each matter group system under the different external fields, and there are vacuum light speed c_i and the minimum time interval dt_i at each local scale to describe the different energy densities for the fields. black hole just describes the observation boundary at the local scale on earth, and each c_i corresponds to each kind of hole in universe. Thus, there is no the singularity with the infinite density, and it is the external field of the matter group system in the center of black hole. Due to EQ16:

Fig.36. multi-scale space-time .

$$1 - \frac{2GM}{rc_i^2} \geq 0$$

So:

$$r \geq \frac{2GM}{c_i^2}$$

This formula describes the boundary of the observation scale. The measurement depends on light wave, so c_i decides the observation boundary, and dt_i describes observation scale.

7. Conclusion: Force is caused by the interaction of all the matters:

Refer to Fig.37 below, it is the schematic diagram of Hetu that comes from Chinese astronomical observation in ancient times. It describes the effects of “like poles repel” and “opposite poles attraction” for the stars, and the stars change to the opposite pole periodically. By the way, the numbers 1~9 in Hetu satisfy EQ04 to describe the connection of coordinate systems. The physical mechanism described by general relativity and quantum mechanics has always been in the motion of the stars in universe.

It does not conform to physical and mathematical laws that the mass of the mass center can be directly measured by the pressure on the surface of an object, without the geometric relation of the object. EQ01 and EQ02 describe the nature of the physical quantities G and M according to the improved calculation method and the result based on the original Cavendish torsion balance experiment, and then the relativity can be explained by the interaction of waves.

Fig.37. Hetu ---- the motion of galaxy.

Gravitational interaction is caused by the attractive effect of all the stable matter group systems (particles) in universe, and Riemann curvature and wave function are equivalent to describe gravitational interaction in the form of coordinate system rotation in maths. EQ04 and EQ07 describe gravitational interaction in the form of physical equations, and they are equivalent to the complex form of wave function. Moreover, EQ10 is the general solution of field equation in general relativity. Thereby, general relativity and quantum mechanics are equivalent to describe gravitational interaction in physics, and EQ14 of the improved Schrodinger equation is equivalent to the field equation of general relativity.

EQ15 of the another form of Dirac equation shows the spin quantum state intuitively, and

the spin angular momentum corresponds to the electric field, so quantum state corresponds to the generalized electric charge at local scale. Electromagnetic field is caused by gravitational interaction, and electromagnetic wave in the vacuum describes the maximum bending effect, so **QED** describes gravitational interaction for electric particle in the variable external field.

EQ16 describes quantum mechanics in the form of the improved gravitational law, and it explains that strong interaction describes the gravitational interaction inside the stable matter group system, and weak interaction describes the gravitational escaping effect between matter group system and external field. EQ17 describes the condition of the symmetry, and EQ18 describes the condition of symmetry breaking. Hence gravitation is the basic physical mechanism of other three fundamental forces.

EQ20 unifies the metric tensor and wave function in the form of complex matrix in the four dimensional space-time coordinate system, so it completes the quantization theory of gravitation in maths. EQ19 describes the connection of scales has the power relationship, so the high-power equation $f(x) = 0$ actually describes the energy conservation at local scale. If the equation has no solution, it means energy conservation does not hold at local scale, and energy changes at the smaller scale dt_i . Hence maths and physics are unified to describe the real world.

In all, nothing moves around another one, and every existence is unique in the world. Force is caused by the interaction of all the matters in universe, and observation is only the effect at the certain scale. Symmetry is instant at some local scale, and symmetry breaking is eternal at all the scales.

Individual Research

Yours sincerely,

Chen Qi

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